

20 **1. Introduction**

21 Amines are nitrogenous bases which are usually synthesized in food by decarboxylation of
22 amino acids (Lange and Wittmann, 2002). When this process is performed by the microbial action of
23 living organisms they are designated as biogenic amines (BAs). Their synthesis in wines is affected by
24 several factors, as the availability of free amino acids of the grapes, the presence of microorganisms
25 with amino acids decarboxylases, or the favorable conditions of such microorganisms for the growth
26 and production of their enzymes (Beneduce et al., 2010; Nouadje et al., 1997; Shalaby et al., 1996).

27 The presence of BAs in foodstuffs has traditionally been used as an indicator of undesired
28 microbial activity, and relatively high amounts of certain BAs have been correlated with deterioration
29 of foods and/or their defective manufacture. The BAs content in wine depends on the processes
30 involved in the vinification, the amino acidic composition of the must, the presence of yeasts and lactic
31 acid bacteria, grape variety and region (García-Villar et al., 2006; Lange and Wittmann, 2002; Nouadje
32 et al., 1997).

33 Besides being a quality index, some BAs can cause health problems, including palpitations,
34 hypo- and hyper-tensive crisis, headache and nausea among others. Its effects can be particularly
35 significant when are consumed in high quantities or when the ability to metabolize them is reduced by
36 the ingestion of monoaminoxidase inhibitor drugs or alcohol, so its determination in alcoholic
37 beverages such as wine is essential (Kirschbaum et al., 1999; Lange and Wittmann, 2002; Romero et
38 al., 2000; Yamamoto et al., 1980). Among BAs in food, histamine (HIM) is the most potentially
39 hazardous one, presenting psychoactive and cutaneous effects, as well as affections in the blood vessels
40 and gastrointestinal problems. Tyramine (TYM) is another important BA, as it increases blood pressure
41 and can cause tachycardia, and also has synergistic effects with HIM; and phenylethylamine (PEA) is a
42 potent migraine inductor. On the other hand, putrescine (PUT) or cadaverine (CAD) are not considered
43 to be toxic but have been described as being able to enhance HIM toxicity, as well as produce negative
44 effects on sensory quality, giving putrefaction and rotting flesh flavor to foodstuffs (Arlorio et al.,

45 1998; Kirschbaum et al., 1999; Lange and Wittmann, 2002; Moreno-Arribas and Polo, 2008; Redruello
46 et al., 2013; Sentellas et al., 2016).

47 This toxicity has led to general agreement that they should not be allowed to accumulate in food
48 (Arlorio et al., 1998; Beneduce et al., 2010). Although there is no legislation dealing with BAs content
49 in wines, some countries recommend limit HIM concentration to a few milligrams per liter (2 - 10 mg
50 L⁻¹) (Busto et al., 1994; García-Villar et al., 2006; Peña-Gallego et al., 2012).

51 Regarding wine consumption in Spain, Spanish people prefer red wines, mainly produced from
52 ‘*Tempranillo*’ grapes, and which have been aged in oak barrels (“www.degustacastillayleon.es,” 2019).
53 In Spanish red wines, and according to the literature, HIM concentrations varied between not detected
54 (n.d.) and 19.6 mg L⁻¹, so those limits were exceeded. PUT, TYM, ethanolamine (ETA) and CAD were
55 also reported in high concentrations (from not detected to 99.9; 59.7; 27.8, and 14.1 mg L⁻¹,
56 respectively). The BAs in the lowest concentrations were agmatine (AGM; n.d. - 6.7 mg L⁻¹), PEA
57 (n.d. - 5.15 mg L⁻¹) and tryptamine (TRY; n.d. - 4.7 mg L⁻¹) (Peña-Gallego *et al.*, 2012).

58 This BAs content can be modified during the storage of the wine. Several studies show the
59 evolution of the BAs profile over time during barrel aging (Jiménez Moreno et al., 2003). However, the
60 consumer may be concerned about the evolution of the BAs once the wine is in their hands and the
61 bottle is opened. As far as we have found, there is only one study analysing the evolution of BAs in
62 opened wine bottles (Ordóñez et al., 2017), in which they studied the evolution of the BAs profile in
63 white wine and red wine of two qualities, for 10 days, under different storage conditions.

64 BAs determination in fermented food is complicated because its low concentrations and the
65 complexity of the samples, being, usually, necessary some clean-up and/or preconcentration steps. BAs
66 are determined by several techniques, being HPLC using C18 columns the most commonly employed.
67 The chromatographic methods developed for its determination have been reviewed by Hernández-
68 Cassou & Saurina in 2011 (Hernández-Cassou and Saurina, 2011), Ordóñez *et al.* in 2016 (Ordóñez et
69 al., 2016) and Papageorgiou *et al.* in 2018 (Papageorgiou et al., 2018). In these methods, a pre- or post-

70 column derivatization step is necessary because these compounds do not have adequate
71 chromatographic or absorption/fluorescence properties. The most used derivatization reagents are *o*-
72 phthaldialdehyde (OPA), fluorenylmethylchloroformate and dansyl chloride (Busto et al., 1994;
73 Hernández-Cassou and Saurina, 2011; Ordóñez et al., 2016).

74 Ultra-High Performance Liquid Chromatography (UHPLC) is becoming very important lately.
75 This technique employs columns with a smaller particle size (minor than 2 μm), as well as greater
76 pressures (up to 600 bar), obtaining better separation capacity, and faster and more sensible results.
77 However, Ordóñez *et al.* (Ordóñez et al., 2016) and Papageorgiou *et al.* (Papageorgiou et al., 2018)
78 have reviewed the recent trends in the determination of biogenic amines in foodstuffs, finding only four
79 methods employing UHPLC in wines. Two of them (Iijima *et al.*, 2013; Latorre-Moratalla *et al.*, 2009)
80 employed ion pair chromatography, derivatizing with OPA post-column, and with fluorescence
81 detection (FD), at 40°C. The other two methods (Jia et al., 2012; Lee et al., 2015) performed a
82 precolumn derivatization with dansyl chloride and a solid phase extraction (SPE) of the sample,
83 detecting the derivatives with MS/MS. The times of analysis ranged between 8 and 21 minutes,
84 obtaining in all cases good analytical figures of merit.

85 Sample treatment is usually done to eliminate possible interferences and to concentrate the
86 analytes. Solvent extraction is the most commonly used technique, being solid phase (micro) extraction
87 the most used. Liquid-liquid extraction and its different variants (liquid-liquid microextraction;
88 dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction; etc.) as well as ionic liquids are also employed. On the other
89 hand, it is also common to add different substances to help clean the sample: polyvinylpyrrolidone
90 (elimination of phenolic compounds and related substances) and acids or organic solvents for protein
91 precipitation (Ordóñez et al., 2016; Papageorgiou et al., 2018).

92 Therefore, in this paper, 8 biogenic amines have been determined and quantified employing an
93 UHPLC-FD in Spanish '*Tempranillo*' red wine, after derivatization with OPA, without sample clean-

94 up, besides filtration. Significant differences in the total biogenic amine content of wine of different
95 aging have been looked for. Also, a study of the influence of storage conditions in the BAs profile had
96 been carried out, increasing the storage time to one month and using three types of red wine of different
97 aging (young, oak and aged wine). Principal Components Analysis and Discriminant Analysis were
98 performed to group and classify the samples.

99

100 **2. Materials and Methods**

101 **2.1 Chemicals**

102 Eight BAs were determined in this study: PUT, HIM, TYM (Sigma), AGM (Alfa Aesar), CAD,
103 TRY, PEA (Aldrich) and ETA (Merck). Octylamine (OCT; Fluka) was used as internal standard (IS).
104 A stock solution of 500 mg L⁻¹ of each BA was prepared (stored refrigerated and in darkness) by
105 solving adequate amounts of the presentation in 0.1 M HCl (Panreac) and was used to daily prepare
106 working analyte solutions. Also, a 0.4 mg mL⁻¹ stock solution of OPA (Aldrich) was weekly prepared
107 in methanol UHPLC-grade (Panreac).

108 Boric acid (Merck) and NaOH (Panreac) were used to weekly prepare a boric acid/sodium
109 borate buffer (pH 10.50; 0.4 M). 2-mercaptoethanol (2-ME; Sigma-Aldrich) was used in the
110 derivatization reaction to improve the sensitivity and stability of the derivatives (Ordóñez et al., 2016;
111 Peña-Gallego et al., 2012).

112 Mobile phase was acetonitrile UHPLC-grade (Sigma-Aldrich) and Trizma® base buffer (2-
113 amino-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-propanediol; Sigma-Aldrich), prepared in a concentration of 0.08 M and
114 adjusted the pH at 8.30 with diluted HCl (Panreac). Before its use, mobile phase was filtered (0.22 µm
115 membrane nylon filter; Teknokroma), and ultrasonicated.

116 The red wines analyzed were obtained from local markets and were kept refrigerated and in
117 darkness, except for the samples employed in the storage conditions study at room temperature. A total
118 amount of thirteen wine brands were taken for this study.

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120 **2.2 Instrumentation and software**

121 An Agilent Model 1260 Infinity High Performance Liquid Chromatograph (Agilent
122 Technologies) was employed to carry out the experiences. It was equipped with an online degasser,
123 quaternary pump (G1311B), column oven compartment (G1316A), autosampler (G1329B), UV-VIS
124 diode-array detector (G1315D) and fluorescence detector (G1321B). Data treatment and instrument
125 control were performed using the ChemStation software. Previous experiences were performed on a
126 Zorbax Eclipse XDB-C18 analytical column (50 x 4.6 mm; 1.8 μm ; Agilent Technologies), but finally
127 a Zorbax Eclipse XDB-C18 analytical column (100 x 4.6 mm; 1.8 μm ; Agilent Technologies) was
128 employed for the analytical separation.

129 pH measurements were performed using a Crison Micro pH 501 meter (Barcelona, Spain),
130 equipped with combined glass/saturated calomel electrode, which was daily calibrated.

131 ACOC software (programmed in MATLAB code) (Galeano Diaz *et al.*, 2007) was used to build
132 the calibration curves and calculate analytical figures of merit. Student t tests of mean comparison
133 were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics v.19 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA). Principal Components
134 Analysis and Discriminant Analysis were performed using XLSTAT software (Addinsoft, Paris,
135 France).

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137 **2.3 Derivatization reaction**

138 The derivatization reaction was slightly modified from the proposed in the official method for
139 determination of BAs (OIV, 2009). Briefly, in a glass tube, 0.4 mL OPA, 0.6 mL methanol, 1.0 mL of
140 boric acid/sodium borate buffer and 0.3 mL of 2-ME were mixed in a vortex. Then, 0.1 mL of IS (5.0
141 mg L^{-1}) was added, and:

142 a) For calibration curve: 0.1 mL aliquots of mixed BAs solutions (concentration between
143 0.019 and 1.0 mg L^{-1}) were added. The solutions were vortexed.

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b) For real samples:

- *Determination of ETA and PUT:* wine sample was diluted in ultrapure water (1:1). Then, 0.05 mL of HCl 0.1 M were placed and vortexed.
- *Determination of the other BAs:* 0.05 mL of wine (without dilution) and 0.05 mL of each BAs addition standard (0.05 – 0.30 mg L⁻¹ of each BA) were placed and vortexed.

2.4 Calibration curve

Calibration curve was established by the internal standard method. To build it, standard solutions were prepared as aforementioned (section 2.3), by addition of aliquots of mixed BAs solutions in variable concentration (0.019 – 1.0 mg L⁻¹). PTFE membrane filters (0.22 µm) were used to filter them before transferred to topaz vials and be immediately injected into chromatographic system. The chromatograms obtained under the optimized conditions were processed using the ChemStation package.

2.5 UHPLC-FD method

The derivatives were eluted at 1.0 mL min⁻¹, using a mobile phase composed by Trizma® base buffer (eluent A) and ACN (eluent B). A gradient mode was established, consisting in a first 0 – 2 min step from 20% to 30% B; 2 – 7 min step from 30% to 40% B; 7 – 10 min step from 40% to 100% B; and a final step 10 – 13 min down to initial conditions (20% B). The column was reequilibrated during 2 min.

5 µL of derivatized sample were injected, and the eluate was fluorimetrically monitored (356/445 nm), using the peak area/IS area ratio as analytical signal.

168 **2.6 Analysis of wine**

169 To determine ETA and PUT a dilution of wine was necessary (1:1, wine:water). The
170 derivatization was carried out as mentioned in paragraph 2.3, by internal standard method, and
171 injecting the samples by triplicate. The concentration of each analyte was determined substituting the
172 analytical signal (BA area/IS area ratio) into the calibration curve.

173 The other BAs could not be determined by the internal standard method, because of the
174 existence of matrix effect, so they were determined by standard addition method combined with IS.
175 Thus, the concentration of each analyte was determined by extrapolation of the curves established
176 between areas ratio (BA area/IS area) versus concentration of BAs added. In this case, no dilution of
177 the sample was necessary. The procedures described previously (sections 2.3 and 2.5) were followed.
178 All the solutions were prepared by duplicate.

179 For its analysis, compounds were identified by comparing retention times with their standards,
180 and by spiking different solutions. The analytical signal employed was the peak area/IS area ratio
181 obtained measuring the fluorescence at 445 nm (exciting at 356 nm).

182 At the end of the working day, the column was cleaned by the injection of 100 μ L of MeOH
183 and going through the column first ultrapure water for 40 minutes and then ACN for 40 minutes.

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185 **2.7 Influence of the storage conditions in the evolution of BAs profile in opened bottles**

186 The influence of the storage conditions in the BAs profile of opened bottles was performed
187 comparing four different conditions: room temperature versus refrigerated, and stopped with cork
188 versus maintained in argon atmosphere. Samples were analyzed as aforementioned (section 2.6). All
189 aliquots were tempered before analysis.

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191 **3. Results and discussion**

192 **3.1 Optimization of chromatographic conditions and evaluation of method performance**

193 Some previous experimental studies were performed and finally a Zorbax Eclipse XDB-C18
194 analytical column (4.6 x 100 mm; 1.8 μm) was employed, using a mobile phase constituted by
195 Trizma® base (eluent A) and ACN (eluent B), in a gradient elution and at 50°C (column temperature).
196 The chosen gradient was as follows: 2 minutes from initial conditions (20% B) to 30% B; a lineal
197 gradient step 2 – 7 min up to 40% B, a lineal gradient step 7 – 10 min up to 100% B, and finally, a
198 lineal gradient step 10 – 13 min down to initial conditions for 2 min. In these conditions, adequate
199 resolution between all peaks was obtained, as can be seen in Figure 1. This figure also shows the
200 chromatogram obtained of a real wine sample.

201 Calibration curves were established between 0.019 and 1.0 mg L^{-1} of BAs to assess the
202 linearity, injecting three times each standard under the optimum conditions. Fluorescence emission was
203 measured at 445 nm, exciting at 356 nm. Calibration curves were built employing the internal standard
204 method. Also, percentage of **recovery** was calculated, and the mean value obtained was $104 \pm 15\%$.
205 These values, together with the figures of merit are listed in Table 1.

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207 ***3.2 Analysis of BAs in wine samples***

208 Calibration curves equations obtained by internal standard method were compared with those
209 obtained by standard addition method combined with IS, observing a matrix effect for all BAs except
210 ETA and PUT. For these two BAs, only a dilution was employed and were determined by internal
211 standard method. The other BAs were found in lower concentrations and no dilution was necessary.
212 Taking into account their matrix effect, standard addition method combined with IS was selected as
213 determination method.

214 At the end of each working day, the column was cleaned injecting 100 μL of MeOH, with a
215 cleaning program consisting on 40 minutes of ultrapure water and 40 minutes of ACN (0.5 mL min^{-1}).

216 In these conditions, more than 250 injections of samples can be injected into the column without loss of
217 efficiency.

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219 **3.3 BAs content in just opened bottles**

220 Several red monovarietal ('*Tempranillo*') young, oak and aged wines were analyzed by the
221 developed method. In Table 2 characteristics of the analyzed wines are shown, and Table 3 shows the
222 concentrations of the BAs found. Total concentration ranged between 22.2 and 73.4 mg L⁻¹, which is in
223 concordance with the values found in the literature, being between 2.49 and 150.64 mg L⁻¹ (Peña-
224 Gallego *et al.*, 2012).

225 In the literature, ETA is only determined in two of fifteen methods found, with concentrations
226 between n.d. and 27.8 mg L⁻¹. However, the developed method permitted to determine ETA and it was
227 found in all the analyzed samples in high concentrations (13.0 – 27.7 mg L⁻¹). PUT also appeared in all
228 samples with a great variability (5.88 and 42.6 mg L⁻¹) as it occurs in other Spanish wines (Peña-
229 Gallego *et al.*, 2012).

230 HIM, AGM, TYM and CAD were found in lower concentrations (n.d.-10.3; 4.3; 4.1, and 2.5
231 mg L⁻¹, respectively). Other Spanish red wines present higher concentrations for all these BAs,
232 especially for TYM which can reach 59.7 mg L⁻¹ (Peña-Gallego *et al.*, 2012). The presence of HIM and
233 TYM in lower concentrations in analyzed wines may present an advantage, since these BAs present a
234 synergistic effect, and are the most dangerous for health.

235 Finally, TRY was not detected in any of the analyzed wines, and PEA was only detected in one
236 of them. Wines of other regions of Spain present concentrations of these BAs that range between n.d.-
237 4.7 and 5.15 mg L⁻¹, respectively (Peña-Gallego *et al.*, 2012).

238 No significant differences have been observed in the total BAs concentration between young
239 and oak red wines. Differences between young and/or oak wines with aged ones could not be
240 calculated because only an aged wine was analyzed.

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242 ***3.4 Influence of the storage conditions in the BAs profile***

243 A study was carried out to check whether there were changes in the profile of BAs according to
244 storage conditions in order, if so, to be able to decide which are the optimal conditions for the storage
245 of wine once the bottles are opened. For this purpose, evolution of BAs profile was monitored for one
246 month in three types of red wine: young (Y6), oak (O6) and aged (A1). Samples were kept under four
247 different conditions: room temperature (25°C) or refrigerated (4°C) and stopped with cork or
248 maintained in Ar atmosphere.

249 For the creation of the Ar atmosphere it was necessary to first remove the air with a vacuum
250 pump, and then, to introduce the Ar in the head space. Ar was used instead of N₂ to create an inert
251 atmosphere because it is denser than air, which implies that less quantity is needed to remove it. Also,
252 it was more difficult to be displaced again by the air.

253 During the studied period of time, few differences have occurred (Table 4). In the young red
254 wine, all BAs (except of TRY) were found. The main BAs present were ETA and PUT, which
255 concentrations slightly decreased along time. Concentrations of AGM and TYM, however, presented
256 the opposite tendency. Total concentrations ranged between 39.8 and 44.0 mg L⁻¹, decreasing a little
257 along time, and showing concentrations more similar to those obtained for the oak red.

258 In the oak red wine, the most important change was the apparition of TYM, which
259 concentration rose up to 6.7 – 7.2 mg L⁻¹ in the seventh day (causing a higher total concentration of
260 BAs content on day 7) to then decrease to 2.70 – 3.0 mg L⁻¹ in the 30th day. CAD also appeared in the
261 sample after the 30 days of storage, in concentrations between 1.1 and 1.9 mg L⁻¹. The other BAs
262 which appeared in the sample (PUT, ETA and HIM) suffered minor changes. PUT followed a tendency
263 to decrease along time, while ETA remained almost constant. Lastly, HIM, decreased slightly from day
264 0 to day 7, and then remained constant. AGM, TRY and PEA were not detected in any of the analyzed

265 samples. Total concentrations ranged between 34.7 and 45.3 mg L⁻¹, being in general lower than in the
266 young red.

267 Finally, aged red presented all BAs except for TRY and PEA. The most important change was
268 the apparition of AGM in the seventh day, which continued to increase along time. TYM presented a
269 decrease in the seventh day, to return to its initial concentrations on day 30th. Others BAs remained
270 almost constant over time, as the total concentrations, which varied between 20.4 and 25.6 mg L⁻¹.

271 It is interesting to note that, according to this study, total concentrations of BAs presented a
272 tendency to decrease as the aging time of the wine increases. Student t-test of mean comparison has
273 been carried out to check if there are significant differences between the means. Assuming that the
274 variances are different (as Levene test was not passed), young wine and oak wine do not present
275 significant differences (as observed in the previous test in section 3.3). On the other hand, aged wine
276 does differ significantly from young and oak wines.

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278 ***3.5 Statistical analysis of the data***

279 Taking into account the previous results, it was decided to study the data statistically, in order to
280 check whether it was possible to classify them as a function of the type of wine and the different
281 storage conditions. Firstly, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was carried out to check whether it
282 was possible to group the different samples according to the type of wine (young, oak or aged) based
283 on the BAs concentration. **Missing data (undetected BAs concentrations) have been replaced by the**
284 **value LOD/2.** By means of the cross-validation method, it was obtained that two principal components
285 explain 91.9% of the variance. Taking into account the loadings, and as is shown in Figure 2A, the first
286 principal component (PC1; 60.7% explained variance) is constituted by the positive contribution of
287 PEA, ETA, TYM, HIM and PUT; while CAD and AGM have a negative effect. The positive effect of
288 the second principal component (PC2; 31.2% explained variance) is formed by the positive
289 contribution of CAD, AGM, PEA and ETA, and the negative effect of TYM, HIM and PUT.

290 Figure 2B shows the scores graph obtained according to the principal components
291 aforementioned, where there are three well-differentiated groups, corresponding to the three types of
292 wine analyzed. Young wine appears in the upper right quadrant, dominated by the contribution of PEA
293 and ETA, that corresponds to the higher values of these two BAs in young wine. Oak wine is grouped
294 in the lower right quadrant, which is influenced by the positive contribution of PC1 and the negative of
295 PC2. This translates into above-average concentrations for TYM, PUT and HIM. Finally, aged wine
296 appears on the left side of the graph, due to their lower than the average concentration in the BAs
297 content.

298 Although the interpretation of the PCA was simple, Varimax rotation was also applied in an
299 attempt to simplify it further. Rotated PC1 was formed by the positive contribution of all the BAs
300 except CAD, AGM and PEA. The contribution of almost all BAs was reduced compared to the non-
301 rotated loadings, obtaining a rotated PC1 based principally on the contribution of PUT (58.2 %) and
302 HIM (30.5 %). With respect to rotated PC2, it had changed and was formed by the positive contribution
303 of all BAs. Rotated PC2 was basically conditioned by ETA (94.4 %), while the rest of BAs had
304 practically no effect. The loadings plot after Varimax rotation is shown in Figure 2C.

305 After rotation, the scores slightly modified their position, with young wines in the upper part of
306 the graph (positive value of PC2), oaks in the lower right quadrant (positive value of PC1) and aged
307 wines in the lower left quadrant (lower concentrations of the mean in all the BAs, especially ETA).

308 Thus, discriminant parameters can be found for each type of wine. ETA discriminates between
309 young (high concentration) and aged wines (low concentration), while high concentrations of PUT and
310 HIM differentiate oak wines.

311 In order to reaffirm the classification obtained by PCA, non-hierarchical and hierarchical cluster
312 analyses have been also carried out.

313 In the case of the non-hierarchical analysis, the k-means method has been employed, which
314 allows the observations to be classified into previously established and independent groups, searching

315 for the minimum residual variance within each group. In this way, three groups were established
316 (young, oak and aged wine), obtaining a 100% correct classification.

317 On the other hand, for the hierarchical cluster analysis, Ward's method was chosen, an
318 agglomerative method that starts from as many groups as observations, and that joins them looking for
319 the minimum residual variance. In this way, homogeneous groups with similar sizes are obtained. After
320 the analysis, three clusters were obtained, corresponding to the three types of wine. Figure 3 shows the
321 dendrogram obtained. As it can be seen, in the case of oak and aged wine, the smaller clusters grouped
322 the observations according to the day of storage. In addition, it can be observed that young and aged
323 wine are more similar to each other than to oak wine, which could be related to the fact that young and
324 aged wine are more related to ETA, and oak wine with PUT and HIM (as discussed previously).

325 Also, the class profile obtained in both cluster analyses revealed that the greatest differences
326 between the three types of wine were found in the concentrations of ETA, PUT and HIM, which was in
327 accordance with the results obtained in PCA with Varimax rotation.

328 In order to analyse the existence of differences within each type of wine according to storage
329 conditions, three Discriminant Analyses (DA) were performed for each wine (type of bottle closing,
330 storage temperature and day of sampling). The results obtained with the three types of wine were
331 similar, and allowed observations to be grouped according to storage conditions.

332 Regarding the classification according to the type of bottle closing used, a single factor
333 composed by the positive contribution of AGM, CAD, HIM, TYM and PEA; and the negative
334 contribution of PUT and ETA, allowed to correctly differentiate the samples stored with cork stopper
335 and those maintained in Ar atmosphere. Samples stored with cork stopper obtain scores located in the
336 left half of the graph (Figure 4A), which corresponds to a greater contribution of those BAs that have a
337 negative influence on the classification factor (PUT and ETA). Wines stored in Ar atmosphere
338 produced higher concentrations of HIM and TYM, two of the most dangerous BAs, so cork stopped

339 wines presented a better BAs profile. In addition, the observations made to the just opened wines were
340 correctly assigned to the cork stopper group (original bottle closing).

341 Similar results were obtained in the classification according to storage temperature. Again, a
342 single factor was enough to discriminate the observations, in this case composed by the positive
343 contribution of all ABs except CAD and HIM. Thus, samples with higher concentrations of these BAs
344 (25°C) appear in the negative zone of the classification factor (Figure 4B). Thus, refrigeration
345 conditions are better to maintain the wines. All observations were correctly classified, and those
346 corresponding to the just opened wines were assigned to the 4°C group, because before their analysis,
347 bottles were stored in refrigeration.

348 Finally, the classification of the observations according to the day of analysis also required a
349 single discriminant factor, consisting of the positive effect of ETA, PUT, HIM and TYM; and the
350 negative of CAD, AGM and PEA. The concentrations of CAD, AGM and PEA increase with storage
351 time, which allows the separation of the observations according to these variables, obtaining the groups
352 of observations further to the left of the graph (Figure 4C) the more time passes (due to a greater
353 negative contribution). Again, the observations were correctly assigned to all types of wine.

354 These results are in agreement with what was obtained by Ordóñez *et al.* (Ordóñez *et al.*, 2017).
355 However, their study only allowed the classification of the samples according to the type of wine and
356 the storage time, not being able to differentiate the samples according to the temperature or type of
357 bottle closing and concluding that the different storage conditions did not produce important changes.
358 In our study, our results show a greater power to discriminate, since small differences in the biogenic
359 amine profile of wines allows their classification based on the type of wine and on the different storage
360 conditions: temperature, bottle closing and storage time. In addition, a more in-depth statistical study
361 has been carried out, which has made it possible to reaffirm the information obtained on the BAs
362 profile of three types of wine. This way, the optimal conditions for the opened wine bottles storage can
363 be selected.

364

365 **4. Conclusions**

366 In this work, several monovarietal ‘*Tempranillo*’ red wines have been analyzed employing an
367 UHPLC method with fluorescent detection, after OPA derivatization and without sample clean-up
368 (besides filtration).

369 The total concentration of BAs in the analyzed wines is in concordance with other Spanish red
370 wines. Also, no significant differences between young and oak total BAs content has been found, but
371 there are significant differences between young/oak and aged wines. On the other hand, a study of the
372 evolution of the BAs profile through time with different storage conditions have been carried out in
373 three types of red wine (young, oak and aged wine), to select the optimal conditions for opened bottles
374 storage. A decreasing tendency in the total concentration of BAs as the aging time of the wine increases
375 has been observed. Statistical analyses have been performed to group the samples according to their
376 aging time employing PCA (without and with Varimax rotation) and cluster analysis (hierarchical and
377 non-hierarchical); and according to the storage conditions using DA. In each case, a single
378 classification factor was employed.

379 Our results suggest that cork stopper and refrigeration are the best conditions to maintain the
380 wines and prevent the increase of HIM and TYM concentrations, the two more hazardous BAs.
381 However, as the production of BAs is linked to microbial activity, further studies, as well as
382 microbiological analysis, are necessary to determine the factors that affect the evolution of BAs profile
383 and set conclusions.

384

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390

391 **References**

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Table 1. Validation parameters for the chromatographic determination of BAs by the developed UHPLC-FD method, using the internal standard calibration. $\lambda_{ex}/\lambda_{em} = 356/445$ nm.

	PUT	AGM	CAD	ETA	HIM	TYM	TRY	PEA
t_R (min)	4.14	4.70	4.81	5.02	5.41	9.73	10.58	10.82
Linear range (mg L⁻¹)	0.074 – 0.75	0.054 – 1.00	0.071 – 0.75	0.036 – 0.30	0.058 – 1.00	0.019 – 0.50	0.038 – 0.50	0.021 – 0.45
Regression equation	y = 3.73 (0.07) x + 0.06 (0.03)	y = 2.22 (0.02) x + 0.009 (0.012)	y = 3.99 (0.07) x + 0.02 (0.03)	y = 8.8 (0.2) x + 0.05 (0.03)	y = 2.61 (0.03) x + 0.02 (0.02)	y = 3.40 (0.02) x + 0.007 (0.006)	y = 3.05 (0.04) x + 0.005 (0.012)	y = 4.53 (0.04) x – 0.007 (0.009)
R²	0.9961	0.9990	0.9965	0.9942	0.9988	0.9995	0.9981	0.9991
Linearity (%)	98.27	99.11	98.35	97.88	99.04	99.41	98.78	99.16
LOD (µg L⁻¹)	22.4	16.3	21.4	10.8	17.6	5.6	11.6	6.3
LOQ (µg L⁻¹)	73.9	53.8	70.6	35.6	58.1	18.5	38.3	20.8
Analytical sensitivity (γ⁻¹) (µg L⁻¹)	16.8	11.7	16.1	8.4	12.6	3.7	7.7	5.2
RSD intraday (%) (low point)	5.24 (0.15 mg L ⁻¹)	2.70 (0.25 mg L ⁻¹)	4.57 (0.15 mg L ⁻¹)	4.24 (0.05 mg L ⁻¹)	3.20 (0.25 mg L ⁻¹)	4.22 (0.15 mg L ⁻¹)	4.40 (0.15 mg L ⁻¹)	6.05 (0.05 mg L ⁻¹)
RSD intraday (%) (high point)	2.37 (0.75 mg L ⁻¹)	1.62 (1.0 mg L ⁻¹)	1.44 (0.75 mg L ⁻¹)	1.45 (0.30 mg L ⁻¹)	1.58 (1.0 mg L ⁻¹)	1.90 (0.50 mg L ⁻¹)	1.49 (0.50 mg L ⁻¹)	1.69 (0.45 mg L ⁻¹)
RSD interday (%) (low point)	5.52 (0.15 mg L ⁻¹)	3.64 (0.25 mg L ⁻¹)	4.65 (0.15 mg L ⁻¹)	2.62 (0.05 mg L ⁻¹)	2.62 (0.25 mg L ⁻¹)	2.22 (0.15 mg L ⁻¹)	3.70 (0.15 mg L ⁻¹)	5.23 (0.05 mg L ⁻¹)
RSD interday (%) (high point)	4.55 (0.75 mg L ⁻¹)	3.02 (1.0 mg L ⁻¹)	5.57 (0.75 mg L ⁻¹)	3.28 (0.30 mg L ⁻¹)	3.28 (1.0 mg L ⁻¹)	2.51 (0.50 mg L ⁻¹)	3.66 (0.50 mg L ⁻¹)	4.25 (0.45 mg L ⁻¹)
Recovery (%)	126.7	96.0	101.0	78.9	109.7	121.3	100.4	95.9

Table 2. Characteristics of the monovarietal ('Tempranillo' grape) analysed wines.

TYPE	WINE	PROCEDENCE	OENOLOGICAL REGION
Young wine	Y1	Puebla Sancho Pérez (Badajoz)	Matanegra (Zafra – Río Bodión)
	Y2	Los Santos de Maimona (Badajoz)	Matanegra (Zafra – Río Bodión)
	Y3	Cañamero (Cáceres)	Cañamero
	Y4	Valdefuentes (Cáceres)	Montánchez
	Y5	Mérida (Badajoz)	Tierra de Barros (Tierra de Mérida – Vegas Bajas)
	Y6	Puebla Sancho Pérez (Badajoz)	Matanegra (Zafra – Río Bodión)
Oak wine	O1	Fuente del Maestre (Badajoz)	Matanegra (Zafra – Río Bodión)
	O2	Bienvenida (Badajoz)	Matanegra (Tentudía)
	O3	Cañamero (Cáceres)	Cañamero
	O4	Valdefuentes (Cáceres)	Montánchez
	O5	Almendralejo (Badajoz)	Tierra de Barros
	O6	Fuente del Maestre (Badajoz)	Matanegra (Zafra – Río Bodión)
Aged wine	A1	Fuente del Maestre (Badajoz)	Matanegra (Zafra – Río Bodión)

Table 3. Concentrations of BAs found in the analysed wines ($\text{mg L}^{-1} \pm \text{SD}$). n.d. = not detected.

WINE	PUT	AGM	CAD	ETA	HIM	TYM	TRY	PEA	TOTAL
<i>Y1</i>	14.1 ± 0.9	2.5 ± 0.1	1.7 ± 0.2	22 ± 1	6.0 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 0.2	n.d.	n.d.	47.7
<i>Y2</i>	13.7 ± 0.5	n.d.	0.59 ± 0.07	22 ± 3	2.4 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.1	n.d.	n.d.	39.4
<i>Y3</i>	14.7 ± 0.9	3.0 ± 0.2	2.4 ± 0.2	20 ± 2	n.d.	2.52 ± 0.09	n.d.	n.d.	42.6
<i>Y4</i>	27.4 ± 0.6	4.3 ± 0.5	2.5 ± 0.3	26 ± 1	7.3 ± 0.5	3.0 ± 0.3	n.d.	n.d.	70.5
<i>Y5</i>	42.6 ± 0.9	n.d.	n.d.	16 ± 1	10.3 ± 0.2	3.3 ± 0.2	n.d.	n.d.	72.2
<i>Y6</i>	12.1 ± 0.4	0.37 ± 0.08	1.5 ± 0.1	23 ± 1	4.7 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.1	n.d.	0.19 ± 0.06	44.1
<i>O1</i>	9.8 ± 0.4	0.97 ± 0.09	0.99 ± 0.08	16 ± 1	5.2 ± 0.2	2.4 ± 0.1	n.d.	n.d.	35.4
<i>O2</i>	6.9 ± 0.3	n.d.	n.d.	18.0 ± 0.3	1.3 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 0.2	n.d.	n.d.	27.6
<i>O3</i>	23 ± 3	2.8 ± 0.2	2.1 ± 0.2	19 ± 2	8.3 ± 0.2	4.1 ± 0.3	n.d.	n.d.	59.3
<i>O4</i>	34.1 ± 0.6	2.5 ± 0.2	1.9 ± 0.3	27.7 ± 0.6	5.3 ± 0.4	1.9 ± 0.4	n.d.	n.d.	73.4
<i>O5</i>	14.0 ± 0.6	n.d.	n.d.	22.3 ± 0.3	1.1 ± 0.3	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	37.4
<i>O6</i>	14.2 ± 0.7	n.d.	n.d.	14.5 ± 0.1	9.1 ± 0.4	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	37.8
<i>A1</i>	5.88 ± 0.04	n.d.	1.5 ± 0.2	13.0 ± 0.4	1.3 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.2	n.d.	n.d.	22.2
YOUNG AVERAGE	20.8	1.7	1.5	21.5	5.1	2.2	n.d.	n.d.	52.8
OAK AVERAGE	17.0	1.0	0.8	19.6	5.1	1.6	n.d.	n.d.	45.1

Table 4. Evolution of the BAs profile in different red wines through storage time in different storage conditions. Concentrations are expressed in mg L⁻¹ (SD). n.d. = not detected.

		DAY	PUT	AGM	CAD	ETA	HIM	TYM	TRY	PEA	TOTAL
YOUNG RED	Argon 4°C	0	12.1 (0.4)	0.37 (0.08)	1.5 (0.1)	22.9 (0.9)	4.7 (0.1)	2.2 (0.1)	n.d.	0.19 (0.06)	44.0
		7	11.1 (0.2)	1.0 (0.2)	1.8 (0.2)	21.6 (0.6)	4.9 (0.3)	2.2 (0.2)	n.d.	0.39 (0.09)	43.0
		30	9.8 (0.4)	0.84 (0.09)	1.5 (0.2)	20.3 (0.3)	4.9 (0.3)	2.5 (0.2)	n.d.	0.5 (0.2)	40.3
	Argon 25°C	0	12.1 (0.4)	0.37 (0.08)	1.5 (0.1)	22.9 (0.9)	4.7 (0.1)	2.2 (0.1)	n.d.	0.19 (0.06)	44.0
		7	11 (1)	0.8 (0.1)	2.0 (0.1)	22 (1)	4.3 (0.2)	2.1 (0.1)	n.d.	0.3 (0.1)	42.5
		30	10.3 (0.3)	1.0 (0.1)	2.1 (0.4)	19.8 (0.7)	4.5 (0.2)	2.1 (0.2)	n.d.	0.5 (0.3)	40.3
	Cork 4°C	0	12.1 (0.4)	0.37 (0.08)	1.5 (0.1)	22.9 (0.9)	4.7 (0.1)	2.2 (0.1)	n.d.	0.19 (0.06)	44.0
		7	11.2 (0.5)	0.5 (0.1)	1.3 (0.2)	22.8 (0.7)	3.7 (0.2)	1.7 (0.2)	n.d.	0.3 (0.1)	41.2
		30	11.2 (0.6)	1.0 (0.2)	1.7 (0.1)	20.2 (0.4)	4.1 (0.2)	2.0 (0.2)	n.d.	0.4 (0.1)	40.6
	Cork 25°C	0	12.1 (0.4)	0.37 (0.08)	1.5 (0.1)	22.9 (0.9)	4.7 (0.1)	2.2 (0.1)	n.d.	0.19 (0.06)	44.0
		7	10.8 (0.6)	0.7 (0.1)	1.9 (0.2)	21.7 (0.8)	4.3 (0.2)	1.99 (0.09)	n.d.	0.3 (0.1)	41.7
		30	10 (1)	0.8 (0.3)	1.7 (0.4)	20.1 (0.6)	4.6 (0.5)	2.2 (0.4)	n.d.	0.4 (0.3)	39.8
OAK RED	Argon 4°C	0	14.2 (0.7)	n.d.	n.d.	14.5 (0.1)	9.1 (0.4)	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	37.8
		7	16.7 (0.9)	n.d.	n.d.	15.9 (0.9)	7.7 (0.2)	6.9 (0.2)	n.d.	n.d.	47.2
		30	9.4 (0.3)	n.d.	1.5 (0.2)	14.0 (0.7)	7.1 (0.2)	2.7 (0.2)	n.d.	n.d.	34.7
	Argon 25°C	0	14.2 (0.7)	n.d.	n.d.	14.5 (0.1)	9.1 (0.4)	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	37.8
		7	15.3 (0.6)	n.d.	n.d.	13.6 (0.9)	6.9 (0.3)	7.2 (0.2)	n.d.	n.d.	43.0
		30	12.9 (0.5)	n.d.	1.5 (0.1)	12.3 (0.3)	7.9 (0.2)	3.0 (0.1)	n.d.	n.d.	37.6
	Cork 4°C	0	14.2 (0.7)	n.d.	n.d.	14.5 (0.1)	9.1 (0.4)	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	37.8
		7	16.5 (0.8)	n.d.	n.d.	15.7 (0.4)	6.4 (0.3)	6.7 (0.2)	n.d.	n.d.	45.3
		30	11.8 (0.4)	n.d.	1.1 (0.1)	15.4 (0.6)	7.3 (0.1)	2.70 (0.08)	n.d.	n.d.	38.3
	Cork 25°C	0	14.2 (0.7)	n.d.	n.d.	14.5 (0.1)	9.1 (0.4)	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	37.8
		7	16.1 (0.7)	n.d.	n.d.	14.3 (0.5)	8.1 (0.3)	6.7 (0.2)	n.d.	n.d.	45.2
		30	12.1 (0.4)	n.d.	1.9 (0.2)	15.8 (0.3)	7.3 (0.2)	3.0 (0.1)	n.d.	n.d.	40.1

AGED RED	Argon 4°C	0	5.88 (0.04)	n.d.	1.5 (0.2)	13.0 (0.4)	1.3 (0.1)	0.5 (0.2)	n.d.	n.d.	22.2
		7	5.3 (0.2)	0.33 (0.07)	1.76 (0.03)	12.1 (0.5)	1.43 (0.05)	0.39 (0.03)	n.d.	n.d.	21.3
		30	5.1 (0.1)	0.89 (0.06)	1.59 (0.09)	11.7 (0.5)	1.60 (0.08)	0.6 (0.1)	n.d.	n.d.	21.5
	Argon 25°C	0	5.88 (0.04)	n.d.	1.5 (0.2)	13.0 (0.4)	1.3 (0.1)	0.5 (0.2)	n.d.	n.d.	22.2
		7	5.4 (0.2)	0.2 (0.1)	1.6 (0.2)	11.9 (0.3)	1.1 (0.1)	0.2 (0.1)	n.d.	n.d.	20.4
		30	6.3 (0.5)	1.04 (0.09)	2.0 (0.2)	14.0 (0.6)	1.8 (0.1)	0.5 (0.2)	n.d.	n.d.	25.6
	Cork 4°C	0	5.88 (0.04)	n.d.	1.5 (0.2)	13.0 (0.4)	1.3 (0.1)	0.5 (0.2)	n.d.	n.d.	22.2
		7	5.7 (0.2)	0.4 (0.1)	2.0 (0.1)	12.1 (0.4)	1.28 (0.07)	0.24 (0.07)	n.d.	n.d.	21.7
		30	5.7 (0.3)	1.1 (0.1)	2.2 (0.2)	13.4 (0.4)	2.0 (0.1)	0.61 (0.07)	n.d.	n.d.	25.0
	Cork 25°C	0	5.88 (0.04)	n.d.	1.5 (0.2)	13.0 (0.4)	1.3 (0.1)	0.5 (0.2)	n.d.	n.d.	22.2
		7	5.6 (0.1)	0.49 (0.07)	1.83 (0.09)	12.1 (0.3)	1.37 (0.06)	0.33 (0.05)	n.d.	n.d.	21.7
		30	5.8 (0.2)	1.1 (0.1)	2.14 (0.09)	12.9 (0.2)	1.7 (0.1)	0.6 (0.1)	n.d.	n.d.	24.2